

Mucin glycoprotein microarray for glycan ligand discovery of bacterial modular proteins

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The intestinal epithelium mucus layer contains extensively O-glycosylated proteins – mucins. How mucin O-glycans are differentially exploited by the microbiota and influence the crosstalk with the human host largely remains to be elucidated at the molecular level¹.

The commensal gut microbiota *Bacteroides caccae* is implicated in the digestion of the colonic mucus layer in low-fibre diet conditions². During growth on mucin-type glycans, *B. caccae* showed an increased expression of modular enzymes, comprising appended non-catalytic carbohydrate-binding modules (CBMs). The hypothesis is that these CBMs facilitate mucin foraging by the bacteria and thereby render the intestinal epithelium susceptible to pathogen infection, promoting states of dysbiosis^{1,2}. To identify glycan ligands targeted by the bacterial CBMs, we developed microarrays containing mucin-enriched glycoprotein samples from diverse human epithelial cell types found in teratomatous tissues of ovarian cystadenomas. They present structurally diverse and complex O-glycans representative of the human O-glycome³.

Initial microarray screening analyses showed differential binding to various mucin-enriched cystadenoma and meconium samples suggesting the recognition of novel O-glycan ligands. Thus, these mucin glycoproteins are an important starting point for the development of mucin O-glycome beam search microarrays⁴ for discoveries of biologically relevant glycan ligands.

References

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